

THE INFLUENCE OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY ON THE ECONOMY AND SOCIO-CULTURAL SPHERE OF THE COUNTRY

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a tour guide of the Registon historic complex

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7783371>

Tourism as a sphere of economic activity is of great importance and has a number of characteristic features. Tourism serves the interests of a person, society as a whole and is a source of income, both at the micro and macroeconomic levels. Tourism is becoming one of the main factors in creating additional jobs, accelerates the development of road and hotel construction, stimulates the production of all types of vehicles, and contributes to the preservation of folk crafts and the national culture of regions and countries. According to the forecasts of the World Tourism Organization, the number of tourist arrivals by 2020 will amount to 1.6 billion people, world tourism income in 2020 will increase to 2 trillion. dollars.¹

Tourism is a very multifaceted branch of the economy, which is one of the main components of income in some countries, affecting the development of their economy and world cooperation.

In many countries, tourism plays a significant role in shaping the gross domestic product, creating additional jobs and providing employment for the population, and enhancing the foreign trade balance. Tourism has a huge impact on such key sectors of the economy as transport and communications, construction, agriculture, production of consumer goods and others, i.e. acts as a kind of catalyst for socio-economic development. In turn, the development of tourism is influenced by various factors: demographic, natural-geographical, socio-economic, historical, religious and political and legal. The economic development of tourism is characterized by impressive data on the world economic market. They show that tourism is the most dynamically developing industry in many countries of the world and that its role in the world economy is constantly growing. International tourism has a powerful impact on employment. The tourism industry is a labor-intensive process, so it employs mostly unskilled workers. However, this does not mean that highly skilled labor is not used in the tourism sector. In this area, new jobs are geographically distributed more widely than in other developing sectors of the economy.

The development of tourism in the world is influenced by scientific and technological progress, improving the quality of life of the population, increasing the duration of free time, vacations, economic and political stability and a number of other factors. Tourism is the fundamental basis of the economy of many developed and developing countries of the world. The basis of the modern tourism market, both in qualitative and quantitative terms, is paid vacations of employees. Recently, the role of business trips, as well as travel of persons of retirement age, has been increasing in tourism. The size and degree of influence of international tourism in the world can be assessed by the following indicators.

¹ Morozov M.A. Economics and entrepreneurship in socio-cultural service and tourism: a textbook for students. - M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2009. – p88

The economic opportunities for the development of tourism on an international scale have created favorable conditions for the development of organizational and economic processes in individual countries. For many of them, international tourism is: 1. the most important source of foreign exchange earnings; 2. a factor stimulating the growth of the balance of payments; 3. a powerful incentive for the development and diversification of many industries (both enterprises and individual industries serving the tourism sector are emerging).

Tourism has an impact on the economy in almost every aspect of the fundamental definition of this area of society. In economic terms, tourism is considered: 1) as a certain set of social relations in the sphere of production, exchange and distribution of products; 2) a part of the national economic complex of a given country, including certain sectoral types of production and economic activity; 3) economic science that studies tourism as a branch of the economy of a country or region (tourism economics); 4) social science that studies behavior in the areas of production of a tourist product, its consumption, distribution and exchange. Economists analyze the processes taking place in these areas, predict their consequences for individuals, organizations and society as a whole; 5) modern economic theory that studies the behavior of people as business entities at all levels of the tourism economic system in the processes of production, distribution, exchange and consumption of tourism services in order to meet human needs with limited resources of the family, firm and society as a whole.

From the point of view of the fundamental economy, tourism is an economic complex, the development of which is largely explained by world economic processes and relations, rather than by immanent (internal) reasons. But tourism is also the most important catalyst for the economic growth of many rapidly developing countries, since it acts as a channel for the redistribution of the gross national product between countries, which is not accompanied by the export (import) of goods and services. In other words, if tourists not only export part of the funds earned in other industries, but also create new jobs in other countries.

Modern tourism as an economic phenomenon: 1. has an industrial form; 2. acts as a tourist product and services that cannot be accumulated and transported; 3. creates new jobs and often acts as a pioneer in the development of new areas and a catalyst for the accelerated development of the national economy; 4. acts as a mechanism for the redistribution of national income in favor of countries specializing in tourism; 5. is a multiplier of the growth of national income, employment and development of local infrastructure and the growth of living standards of the local population; 6. characterized by a high level of efficiency and a quick return on investment; 7. acts as an effective means of protecting nature and cultural heritage, since it is these elements that form the basis of its resource base; 8. compatible with almost all sectors of the economy and human activities, since it is their differentiation and discreteness that create the difference in the potentials of the recreational environment, which causes people to need to change places and learn.

Thus, international tourism will continue to develop despite the risk of an economic downturn, as tourism demand has its own determinants. It is also undeniable that the international disparity in the tourism sector is significant. To achieve equal success in the world, new approaches to encourage the development of tourism should be based on international

cooperation. Therefore, international cooperation and agreements between the key components of tourism (hotels, transport, tourism companies) should guarantee the future development of the industry.

Tourism - as a type of socio-cultural activity and as an industry that produces services necessary to meet the needs that arise in the process of travel, is the most important sector of the economy, the further development and improvement of which will contribute to an increase in state revenues.

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